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Appreciation of Muttusvami Dikshitar's Navāvaraṇa Kṛti in the Raga Śankarabharanam.

Mr. Ratheesh P R¹

Abstract

Muttusvami Dikshitar, who is one of the Trinity of Carnatic Music, was born in Thiruvarur. He was a great Devi Upasaka and out of his devotion to Kamalāmba, the celebrated deity at the famous Tyagaraja temple in Thiruvarur, Dikshitar has composed nine compositions on Goddess Kamalāmbika. These compositions show his proficiency in Sanskrit language especially Sri Cakra and its Āvaraṇa-s. Though these compositions are nine in number, they are preceded with a Dhyana kṛti and succeeded with a Mangala kṛti. Navāvaraṇa kirtana-s are composed based on the Vibhakti (case ending) of Sanskrit grammar. Muttusvami Dikshitar's devotional outpourings towards Goddess Kamalāmba can be seen in these compositions. The composition 'Sri Kamalāmbikayā' composed in the raga Śankarabharanam is taken here for analysis. This is an attempt to analyse the melodic, rhythmical, textual and philosophical aspects of the particular composition.

Keywords

Āvaraṇa, Kṛti, Pallavi, Anupallavi, Caraṇam

Introduction

Thiruvarur is musically famous for the birth of Trinity of South Indian Classical Music. Trinity of Carnatic Music i.e., Tyagaraja, Muttusvami Dikshitar and Syama Sastri can be considered as the founders of present Carnatic Music tradition in Thiruvarur. Among them, Muttusvami Dikshitar was the youngest. Muttusvami Dikshitar was born to Ramasvami Dikshitar and Subbulakshmi in the year

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1775. Ramasvami Dikshitar was himself a musician and composer. Muttusvami Dikshitar had his initial lessons from his father. Before he was sixteen, he became proficient in Vedanta, Mimamsa, Jyotisha, Tantra, Mantra, Kavya, Alankara and in different languages like Sanskrit, Telugu etc. He was adept in playing the Vina.

Highly impressed by the musical caliber of Ramasvami Dikshitar, Muddukrishna Mudaliar, the Zamindar of Manali, appointed Ramasvami Dikshitar as the court musician. So, the family had to shift to Manali. During the stay at Manali, Chidambaranath Yogi from Varanasi, who initiated Ramasvami into Srividya Cult, happened to hear Muttusvami Dikshitar sing and play the Vina. The Yogi requested Ramasvami to send the boy with him. With much hesitation, Ramasvami finally sent Muttusvami with the Yogi. Muttusvami stayed at Varanasi for about five years, practised Srividya and obtained the 'Aṣṭasiddhis'. The Srividya name of the Yogi was 'Srinatha', and that of Muttusvami Dikshitar was 'Chidanandanatha'. Both names have mentioned in his first kṛti, Sri Nathādi Guruguho'.

At the end of the stay at Varanasi, the Guru told him that it was the time for their separation. The Yogi asked him to have a dip in Ganges and see what he received. Dikshitar obeyed him and he was surprised to find a Vina with the Yālimukha turned upwards and the word Srirama inscribed on it in Sanskrit. The Guru then shook off his mortal coil in the Ganga and attained Moksha.

From Varanasi, Muttusvami Dikshitar came to Tiruttani temple, the holy shrine attributed to Lord Subrahmanya. There, once he was reciting the 'Subrahmanya Panchadasaka Mantram', Lord Subrahmanya in the guise of an old man appeared before him and put a sugar candy into his mouth. The sugar candy was the representation of knowledge. When he opened his eyes, it is said that he was alarmed to see Lord Subrahmanya moving away with His consorts Valli and Devasena. Inspired by this, he began to compose his first kṛti 'Sri Nathādi Guruguho' in the raga Mayamalavagaula. From then Muttusvami hailed Lord Subrahmanya as his Guru and adopted 'Guruguha' as his mudra in the compositions.

The contributions of Muttusvami Dikshitar to the Carnatic music

world is noted for its quality, quantity and variety. His compositions count to more than 500 and they include Varnams, Kṛtis, Ragamalikas and Group kṛtis. Muttusvami Dikshitar is credited to have composed many group kṛti-s in praise of various deities. Even though these compositions are considered as a group, each kṛti has its own individuality and charm. They can be presented as individual kṛti-s. When the number of kṛti-s in a group exceeds eight, he has used the Vibhakti style.

Navāvaraṇa Kṛti-s

‘Āvaraṇa’ literally means that which is concealed. The nine āvaraṇas in one’s body conceal the Brahma Jivan. Tantra Sastra describes elaborate rituals for devi worship. In order to reach Her, one must pass through nine āvaraṇas and perform certain rituals at each stage which have different names and powers. These nine stages are called Navāvaraṇas. Srīcakra is the yantra that has supernatural powers. The spiritual ascent of the yogi is from the outer cover inwards, the highest state being the centre. The centre or the Bindu represents the point of concentration of all creative forces. ‘Āvaraṇa Devatas’ represent the different states of our mind while practising Srividya. The nine Āvaraṇas, the devatas represented and the different stages of mind are shown below:

Avaranas	Devatas	State of mind
Bhupara	Prakata Yogini	Wakefulness
16 petalled lotus	Gupta Yogini	Dream
8 petalled lotus	Guptatara Yogini	Profound sleep
14 triangles	Sampradaya Yogini	Deliberation of God
Outer 10 triangles	Kulottirna Yogini	Proximity to God
Inner triangles	Nigarbha Yogini	Upadesa
8 triangles	Rahasya Yogini	Meditation
Central triangles	Atirahasya Yogini	Profound meditation
Bindu	Paraparahirahasya Yogini	Savikalpa samadhi

Kamalāmba Navāvaraṇam

Muttusvami Dikshitar was a great Devi Upasaka and out of his devotion to Kamalāmba, the celebrated deity in the famous Tyagaraja temple at Thiruvavur, he has composed nine compositions on Goddess Kamalāmbika. Nine kṛti-s on different āvaraṇas are preceded by a dhyana kṛti and ended with a Mangalam. In total, there are 11 compositions in this group which are given below with vibhakti-s used.

Sl. No.	Kṛti	Raga	Tala	Vibhakti
1	Kamalāmbikē	Todi	Rupakam	Sambōdhanā
2	Kamalāmbā Sama rakṣatu	Ananda bhairavi	Tripata	Prathamā
3	Kamalāmbām Bhajarē	Kalyani	Adi	Dvitiyā
4	Sri Kamalāmbikāyā	San- karabhara- nam	Rupakam	Tṛtīyā
5	Kamalāmbikāyai	Kamboji	Khanda Ata	Caturthī
6	Sri Kamalāmbikāyāh	Bhairavi	Jhampa	Pañcamī
7	Kamalāmbikāyāstava	Punnaga varali	Rupakam	Ṣaṣṭī
8	Sri Kamalāmbikāyām	Sahana	Tripata	Saptamī
9	Sri Kamalāmbike avava	Ghanta	Adi	Sambōdhanā
10	Sri Kamalāmba jayati	Ahiri	Rupakam	All vibhakti-s
11	Sri Kamalāmbike	Sri	Khanda Eka	Sambōdhanā

The present study focuses on analysing one of the Navāvaraṇa kṛtis of Muttusvami Dikshitar i.e., the third āvaraṇa kṛti 'Sri Kamalāmbikāyā' in the raga Śankarabharanam set to Rūpaka tāla.

Pallavi

śrī kamalāmbikāyā kaṭākṣitōham

saccitānanda paripūrṇa brahmāsmi

Anupallavi

pāka śasanādi sakala dēvatā sēvitayā
 pankajāsanaḍi pañcakṛtyākṛt bhāvitayā
 śōka hara catura padayā
 mūka mukhya vākpradayā
 kōkanada vijaya padayā
 guru guha tatrai padayā

Caranam

ananga kusumādyashta saktyākārayā
 aruṇa varṇa samkṣōbhaṇa cakrākārayā
 ananta kōtyaṇda nāyaka śankara nāyikayā
 ashta vargātmaka guptatarayā varaya
 anangādyupāsitayā ashta daḷābja sthitayā
 dhanurbāṇa dhara karayā dayā sudhā sāgarayā

Thematic Study

This composition refers to third Āvaraṇa – Aṣṭadalam (8 petals). The Chakram is ‘Sarvasamkṣobhaṇa chakra’ (agitates all) the Yogini is Gupta Tara Yogini. The mental state is Suṣupti, the Chakra Īswari is Tripura Sundari and the Śaktis are the eight starting with Ananga Kusuma.

Pallavi

Sri Kamalambika has cast Her gracious glance on me, and now I am identified (asmi) with the nature of Absolute (paripūrṇa) Brahman (brahma), the fullness of existence (sat), consciousness (chit) and bliss (ānanda).

Anupallavi

Indra (pāka śasana) and other (ādi) celestials (sakala devatā) attend (sevitayā) on Her.

She is adored (bhāvitayā) by Brahma (pankajāsana) and others (ādi) who perform the Pancakṛtya, the five (panca) cosmic acts (kṛt) creation (sṛṣṭi), protection (sthiti), destruction (samhāra), delusion or screening (tirodhāna) and grace (anugraha).

Her feet are adroit (catura) at removing (hara) grief (śōka).

She endowed (pradayā) the gift of speech (vāk) in Mūka and

made him a Kavi.

Her victorious (vijaya) feet (padayā) are like red lotus (kōkanada).

She is the embodiment of the three-word (traī-padayā) mantra Tat-Tvam-Asi imparted by Guruguha.

Caraṇam

Her form (ākārayā) is of eight (aṣṭa) Śaktis (śaktyā), Anangakusuma and the rest.

She is the color (varṇa) of dawn, Aruṇa (i.e., red colour).

She is enshrined (kārayā) in the Samkṣobhaṇa Chakra.

She is the consort (nayikayā) of Śankara, who is the Lord (nāyaka) of innumerable universes (ananta koṭyananda).

She is of the nature (ātmaka) of eternal and hidden (gupta) Aṣṭavarga, the eight (aṣṭa) groups (varga) of alphabets.

She is worshipful (tarayā varayā), seated (sthitayā) on an eight-petalled (aṣṭa-daḷa) lotus (abja).

She is worshiped (Anangādyupāsītayā) by Cupid and others.

She holds (dhara) in her hand (karayā) a bow (dhanur) and arrows (bāṇa).

She is an embodiment (sāgarayā) of the nectar (sudha) of compassion (dayā).

Musical analysis

Pallavi: Pallavi starts in madhyastayi Ṣadjam with Samagraham. Phrases in Pallavi cover one full octave from mandra pancamam to Madhya pancamam. First pada has four avarta-s and three variations in the sangati. Second pada starts in atīta graham. Pallavi concludes with the second pada itself.

Anupallavi: Anupallavi starts in Madhya pancamam. There is a Samvādi relationship between the graha svara-s of Pallavi and Anupallavi (fifth note). Each pada consists of four avarta-s. This is followed by a madhyamakala saḥityam which has four pada-s, each pada consists of one avarta. Phrases in the anupallavi go upto Tarastayi ṛṣabham. Pallavi is being repeated after the madhyamakala saḥityam.

Caranam: Caranam starts in Madhya Shadjam. It is quite interesting that all the sections of this kṛti start either in Shadjam

or Pancamam since these are the most important svara-s for the raga Śankarabharanam. First four padas of Caranam are having four Avarta-s each followed by the madhyamakala sahityam which has four padas, each pada consists of one avarta. The mudra ‘Guruguha’ comes in the Anupallavi. Phrases in the caranam cover all the three stayi-s from Mandra Pancamam to Tara Gandharam.

Literary Analysis

Svarākṣara

Pancamam: Pākaśasana
Pankajāsana
Śōka hara catura **padayA**
mūka mukhya vAk-**pradayA**
guru guha tat-trai-**padayA**

Sūcīta svarākṣara:

Ṣaḍjam: Śri Kamalambikaya
sr,,g,mg
Śōkahara
ś,sn

Prāsa:

Adyaksara Prāsa: In the Carana,
Anangakusuma
Aruṇa varṇa
Ananta
Aṣṭavarga
Dvitīyakṣara Prāsa: In the Anupallavi,
Pāka śāsanādi
Pankajāsanādi
Śōkahara
Mūkamukhya

First phrase of Caranam and its Madhyamakāla resemble the same word, ‘Ananga’.

Antyākṣara Prāsa: All pada-s (lines) of Anupallavi and Caranam end with the syllable ‘yā’.

Conclusion

The raga chosen by the composer for the third āvaraṇa kṛti is Śankarabharanam. The state of mind for the third āvaraṇa is Suṣupti or Profound sleep. The raga Śankarabharanam is an apt selection for the composition since it evokes the tranquil mood throughout. The

elongation of Sahitya syllables well suited to the tempo of the raga. Muttusvami Dikshitar carefully handled the gamaka-s in the raga which supports the flow of music. The selection of tala is also equally important for the presentation of composition. He selected Rūpaka tala in 2 kala (slow tempo) in order to suit the kālapramaṇam of the song. This single composition shows Muttusvami Dikshitar's proficiency in Music, Sanskrit and related subjects.

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